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A Study on the general Mental ability of physical education students at (AMU),U.P. India.

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Abstract

This study aimed to measure and compare the general mental ability of M.P. Ed. Students in the first and third semesters, whose genders were male and female. The random sample technique was used for this study. From the Department of Physical Education, Aligarh Muslim University (AMU), 44 samples (N = 44) were taken for the study. Dr. Rama Tiwari and Mrs. General's mental ability was measured by The Roma Pals Questionnaire, which contained seventy (70) questions with eight categories: genius, gifted, superior, bright, average, dull, broader line, defective, and feeble-minded. This category was computed in terms of the mean score of the person. The gender-based and overall general mental ability of M.P. Ed. I and III semester students were measured and compared using the parametric 't' -test. The findings revealed no discernible difference between.

M.P. Ed., I, and III Sem. Students were combined and gender. Overall, the results of this study were nonsignificant. The data analysis indicates nonsignificant differences in the general mental ability among M.P. Ed. first and third-semester students of the Aligarh Muslim University Department of Physical Education.

Keywords

General mental ability, postgraduate students, boys and girls, sports, general life, decision-making, success,

Introduction

General mental ability is defined as intelligence. Many psychologists believe that intelligence is a group of abilities rather than a single special ability. David Wechsler defined that "intelligence is the manifestation of the ability of people to adjust effectively to the situation." Intelligence "is the aggregate or global capacity of the individuals to act purposefully, think rationally, and act effectively." Burt "Intelligence is the power of readjustment to relatively novel situations by organizing new psycho-physical combinations." It is an inborn, all-around mental ability." Terman: "An individual is intelligent in proportion as he can carry on abstract thinking."

Thorndike "Intelligence is a power of beneficial responses from the point of truth and fact. It is the ability of a former association or connection to form." Thurstone's "Intelligence is a movement from trial and error towards increasing abstract control." Calvin. An individual possesses intelligence in the sense that he has learned or can learn to adapt to his environment. According to Piaget, "Intelligence constitutes the state of equilibrium towards which tend all the successive adaptations of a sensorimotor and cognitive nature, as well as all assimilatory and accommodatory interactions between the organism and the environment." Intelligence involves (i) The tendency to take and maintain a definite direction; (ii) The capacity to make adaptations to attain a desired end; and (iii) the power of self-criticism. Spearman's intelligence is the general ability to reason and think. Intelligent activity of Alicia Heim knowing what's necessary in a particular situation and responding appropriately to it. Total or worldwide ability to behave purposefully in the environment, to reason logically, and to perform well is Wechsler.

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Moreover, higher mental toughness athletes are always sophisticated in the interpretation of the involved complicated game situations and the creation of strategies other than the opponents' moves. Focus: The tendency to concentrate on the job and clear distractions depends on general mental aptitude. This is essential for delivering results under duress and in pivotal competitive times.

Athletes have to filter out inappropriate impulses and focus attention on relevant aspects of the game. By improving selective attention, cognition improves performance. Other successful athletes are good problem solvers who, when facing some unexpected challenge or a sudden change in a situation, can alter their game plan. In analytical thought, athletes analyze their performance for areas of weakness and, therefore, make much-needed changes. General mental ability enables an athlete to acquire new skills and techniques faster and more effectively than his peers. Cognitive skills help with the acquisition and processing of new knowledge.

Strong mental abilities can support the athlete in remembering extremely intricate patterns and strategies that should be implemented during competition. Emotional control and cognitive skills are two sides of the same coin, working side by side, allowing athletes to better cope with stress, anxiety, and frustration all of which are required to support high performance. Emotional strength is amplified by improved cognitive functioning, which allows the athlete to rebound from adversity and remain positive. Some sports necessitate rapid visual processing in such actions as following moving objects, for example, in following the movements of an opponent or a ball.

General mental ability allows the athlete to better develop spatial awareness and visual perception. This enables an athlete to respond more quickly and efficiently to situations since he or she uses his or her cognitive processing more swiftly. Team sports enhance teamwork and have improved strategy execution in teams since they help teammates become better communicators and coordinators with one another. Effective leaders are usually strong-minded cognitive athletes who inspire and manage their teammates through strategic thinking and decision-making. A stronger mental ability will aid a player in reviewing and thinking about a stressful condition, which may help decrease pressure and therefore improve performance.

Objective of study

Stoddard According to the definition, intelligence is the skill to do things that are (1) hard, (2) complicated, (3) abstract, (4) 18 economies, (5) adaptable to a goal, (6) socially valuable, and (7) lead to original ideas, and to keep doing these things in situations that require focus and resistance to emotional factors.

Review of Literature

General mental ability refers to a candidate's mental ability to understand verbal information, become conscious and process numbers and information in graphical format, think laterally, and make a logical connection between words and concepts to understand crucial data. Other terms such as intelligence, IQ, general cognitive ability, and general mental ability are also used interchangeably to mean the same thing as general intelligence. This general mental ability is what underlies specific mental skills. The individual's mental ability to complete tasks or make adjustments to work successfully. Such ability is formed by sensory or mental acts; it can be innate or acquired by learning. Moreover, there are general abilities representing a common factor, in different degrees, with all the specialized abilities or a group of them.

Badawy (1988), Intelligence, also known as general mental ability, as an explanatory construct, has been somewhat ignored in the study of human development in general and leader development in particular. Studies of intelligence reveal it to be a strong predictor of academic, career, and life success. Other terms such as intelligence, IQ, general cognitive ability, and general mental ability are also used interchangeably to mean the same thing as general intelligence. This general mental ability is what underlies specific mental skills in areas such as spatial, numerical, mechanical, and verbal abilities. In his study, Singh (2013) found that there were insignificant differences between female national players, inter-school players, and non-players on the variable general mental ability. Insignificant differences were found between male national players and female national players in terms of the variable general mental ability. Insignificant differences were found between male and female inter-school players in terms of the variable of general mental ability. Giri (2021), in his study, found that school-going children can improve their general mental ability through the regular practice of Bhramari Pranayama. Bhramari Pranayama's training is very helpful in improving the general mental abilities of school-going students.

Vadoliya (2018) in his study found that there was an insignificant main impact of the sex variable on mental ability, but there was no significant main impact of the type of work variable on mental ability. There was a nonsignificant internal effect of sex and type of

work variables on mental ability. Otherwise, there was a positive correlation between self-consciousness and mental ability; there was a positive correlation between moral value and mental ability. Desai (2020), in his study, found that the students of government-aided and unaided secondary schools have different mental ability scores. The students of rural and urban secondary schools have similar mental abilities. Students in government and assisted secondary schools have similar mental abilities. Students in government secondary schools have higher mental ability scores than those in aided secondary schools. The mental ability scores are significantly higher in educated parents of students in secondary schools as compared to illiterate parents of secondary schools.

Mishra (2021), in his study, found that the mental capacity of students using the 7E Model is substantially higher than that of the traditional method. The students taught by the 7E Model are substantially higher than the students taught by the traditional method. their achievement in Algebra George (2003), in his study, found that the interaction of levels of stress and place of residence is seen to insignificantly influence only the number of tuitions and verbal mental ability. There is a significant difference in the numerical mental ability of urban and rural adolescents. There is a significant difference in the overall mental abilities of urban and rural adolescents. Sidaran (2022), in his study, found that mental ability and attitude towards mathematics have influenced the mathematical ability of higher secondary students. The study also reveals that demographic variables are predictable factors. Based on these results, it was suggested that stakeholders should equip schools with facilities that would develop and maintain students' mental ability, as it is a good predictor of students' mathematical ability. A research study conducted by Al-Ghamri in 2007 found a significant positive correlation between the scores of students' mental ability (intelligence) and their age in total tests and all subtests.

Senthilnathan (2014), in his study, found that there is a significant average positive relationship between political knowledge and the mental ability of higher secondary school students. There is a significant positive-moderate relationship between political knowledge and mental ability. There is a nonsignificant average positive relationship between study involvement and higher secondary school students' mental ability. Prepare themselves for competition by imagining themselves performing well in it. Create and use mental images that are detailed, specific, and realistic. During the competition, use imagery to prepare for action and recover from incorrect and low-quality performances. Certainly, general mental ability, often referred to as cognitive ability or intelligence, plays a significant role in sports.

General mental ability dominates the performance and development of a sports person. Sport often has periods during which athletes must make decisions under the stress of changing situations. General mental ability enables quick, accurate decision-making to select appropriate actions during these high-pressure moments.

Methodology

The total number of participants included 44 postgraduate students of physical education from Aligarh Muslim University. The age group was 24 - 25 years. Of the 44 students, 22 (15 male and 7 female) were M.P. Ed. first semester and 22 (15 male and 7 female) were M.P. Ed. third-semester students. With great interest in the classroom, all students agreed to take part in the study. The data collection system was offline. So, the questionnaire was distributed to the students hand-to-hand in both classrooms (M.P. Ed., first semester and third semester). Every student received the questionnaire and properly and carefully filled it out, and all questionnaires were collected after them. Data was collected using a 70-item questionnaire. It was developed by Dr. Roma Pal and Dr. Rama Tiwari, and it was used to collect data. Nine categories and 70 questions i) Genius; ii) Gifted; iii) Superior; iv) Bright; v) Average; vi) Dull; vii) Broder line; viii) Defective; ix) Feebleminded. The researcher provided a score based on the subjects' responses. Each question below consisted of four alternative options for various types of questions. For every written answer, the numbering producer gave 1 mark. A parametric t-test was used to find out the 'p'-value and the 't'-value, such as mean and standard deviation, means hypothesis testing. For this study, we also used two-tailed t-tables.

Result and Discussion

Table No. 1
Comparison of scores of male and female students, M.P. Ed.
First semester on "General Mental Ability"

S.No.	Name of the class M.P. Ed, I Sem	Total number of students	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
1	Male	15	128.80	19.81	0.11	0.91
2	Female	07	127.28	32.74		

df = 20 out of 22, t = 2.08

It is observed in Table No. 1 that M.P. Ed. I Sem male and female students scored respectively superior in general mental ability because the mean values are 128.80 and 127.28, according to norms. The calculated t-value is 0.11, which particularly indicates a nonsignificant difference between M.P. Ed. I Semester male and female students because the obtained t-value of 0.11 is less than the t-table value of 2.08.

Table No. 2
A comparison of male and female students' scores in M.P. Ed.
Third-semester male and female students on "General mental ability"

S.No.	Name of the class M.P. Ed, III Sem	Total number of students	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
1	Male	15	128.16	30.12	-2.75	0.01
2	Female	07	158.43	21.88		

df = 20 out of 22, t = 2.08

It is indicated in Table No. 2 that M.P. Ed., III Semester male and female students scored separately superior and genius in general mental ability because the mean values are 128.16 and 158.43, according to norms. The calculated t-value is -2.75, which exactly indicates a nonsignificant difference between M.P. Ed. III Semester male and female students because the obtained t-value of 2.75 is less than the t-tabled value of 2.08.

Table No. 3
Comparison of scores of M.P. Ed., first-semester male, and M.P. Ed.,
third-semester male students on "General mental ability"

S.No.	Name of the class M.P. Ed, I Sem	Total number of students	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
1	Male	15	128.80	19.81	0.06	0.94
2	Male	15	128.16	30.12		

df = out of 30, t = 2.08

Table No. 3 shows that M.P. Ed., I and III Semester male students scored superior in general mental ability because the mean values are 128.80 and 128.16, respectively, according to norms. The calculated t-value is 0.06, which particularly indicates a nonsignificant difference between M.P. Ed., I, and III Semester male students because the obtained t-value is 0.06, which is less than the t-tabled value of 2.08.

Table no. 4
Comparison of scores of students of M.P. Ed. first semester and M.P. Ed.
The third semester combined students on "general mental ability"

S.No.	Name of the class	Total number of students	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
1	M.P. Ed, I Sem Boys + girls	22	128.15	24.42	-1.14	0.26
2	M.P. Ed, III Sem Boys + girls	22	137.79	30.82		

df = 42 out of 44, t = 2.00

It is indicated in Table No. 4 that M.P. Ed., I, and III Semester students scored separately as gifted and superior in general mental ability because the mean value is 128.15 and 137.79 according to norms. The calculated t-value is -1.14, indicating a nonsignificant difference between M.P. Ed. I and III Semester students, as the obtained t-value of -1.14 is less than the t-tabled value of 2.00.

Table No. 5
Comparison of M.P. Ed. Female students' scores on "general mental ability"
in the first and third semesters

S.No.	Name of the class M.P. Ed, I and III Sem	Total number of students	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
1	Female	07	127.28	32.74	-2.09	0.05
2	Female	07	158.43	21.88		

df = 12 out of 14, t = 2.17

It is observed in Table No. 5 that M.P. Ed., first-semester, and third-semester female students scored separately superior and genius levels in general mental ability because the mean value is 127.28 and 158.43, according to norms. The calculated t-value is -2.09, indicating a nonsignificant difference between M.P. Ed., first-semester female, and third-semester female students because the obtained t-value of -2.09 is less than the t-tabled value of 2.17.

Table No. 6
Comparison of scores of M.P. Ed., first-semester male and M.P. Ed.,
third-semester female students in "General mental ability"

S.No.	Name of the class	Total number of students	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
1	M.P. Ed I Sem male	15	128.80	19.81	-3.04	0.01
2	M.P. Ed III Sem female	07	158.43	21.88		

df = 20 out of 22, t = 2.08

It is observed in Table 6 that M.P. Ed., first-semester male, and third-semester female students scored respectively inferior and average levels in general mental ability. because the mean values are 128.80 and 158.43, according to norms. The calculated t-value is -3.04, indicating a nonsignificant difference between M.P. Ed., first-semester male, and third-semester female students because the obtained t-statistic is 3.04, less than the t-table value of 2.08

Table No. 7
On "General mental ability," compare the scores of female students in M.P. Ed., first semester, and male students in M.P. Ed., third semester.

S.No.	Name of the class	Total number of students	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
1	M.P. Ed, I Sem female	07	127.28	32.74	-0.05	0.95
2	M.P. Ed, III Sem male	15	128.16	30.12		

df = 20 out of 22, t= 2.08,

It is observed in Table No. 7 that M.P. Ed., first-semester female, and third-semester male students scored each at an inferior level in general mental ability because the mean values are 127.28 and 128.16, according to norms. The calculated t-value is -0.05, indicating a nonsignificant difference between M.P. Ed., first-semester female, and third-semester male students because the obtained t-statistic is -0.05, less than the t-table value of 2.08.

Discussion

After analyzing the data, it was found that there is a nonsignificant difference in general mental ability between M.P. Ed. First-semester male and female students. Nonsignificant differences were found between M.P. Ed. third-semester male and female students, which is a match for Singh's (2013) study; he also found that no significant differences were found between male and female inter-school players in terms of the variable of general mental ability, and Vadoliya (2018) in his study found that there was a nonsignificant, in the main impact of the type of work variable on mental ability. For both genders, male and female, there is also a negligible difference between the first and third semesters of M.P. Ed. There is a nonsignificant difference between M.P. Ed. first- and third-semester male students, accompanied by a nonsignificant difference between M.P. Ed. first and M.P. Ed. Third-semester female students in general mental ability. General mental ability affects nonsignificant differences in class to class, and gender to gender. The researcher finds that in this research, there is no significant difference in general mental ability between students of physical education at Aligarh Muslim University (AMU). Lastly, in Tables 6 and 7, we did not find any differences for the male students of M.P. Ed. I Semester and III Semester for female students and the female students of M.P. Ed. I Semester and III Semester for male students.

Conclusion

In the conclusion part, we can say that the analysis finds no significant difference in the general mental ability among the students belonging to various semesters and gender groups of M.P. Ed. Contrary to the above, in the study by Singh in the year 2013, findings are arrived at through his data analysis as follows: Likewise, insignificant differences have also been found among the female national players and inter-school players in his study. Nonsignificant differences were observed in support of Vadoliya's (2018) findings, which found that the sex variable had a nonsignificant main impact on mental ability. However, no significant differences were found between male and female M.P. Ed. first- and third-semester students, which is consistent with previous research. Previous studies did not find significant differences between male and female M.P. Ed. first- and third-semester students. This study emphasizes the complexity of the general mental ability of all M.P. Ed. students (male and female) in the first and third semesters.

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